

Photochemical Study of Cobalt(III) Complexes in Mixed Aqueous Glycol System

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Homolytic metal-ligand bond fission in the excited state of (LMCT) character leads to redox decomposition. Some differences in opinions are there in the mechanism of redox decomposition regarding whether or not the radical pair generated by the excited state bond fission can undergo geminate recombination or diffusive separation during the life-time of the excited state in the solvent cage. Normally with solvents of increasing viscosity the diffusive separation of the radicals becomes restricted with a reduction in quantum yield. In our case, however, studies with $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)\text{HC}_2\text{O}_4](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{C}_2\text{O}_4]\text{ClO}_4$ with two different composition of ethyleneglycol-water at three different wavelengths, have resulted in an increase in the quantum yield at pH 3.72.

The photochemistry of Co^{III} complexes is characterised by the extensive occurrence of redox decomposition reactions¹. It is now generally agreed that redox decomposition arises from homolytic metal-ligand bond fission occurring in the excited states of ligand to metal charge transfer band. However, there has been some dispute in the mechanism of 'redox decomposition'². It seems that the controversial point concerns whether or not the radical pair generated by the excited state homolytic bond fission can undergo geminate recombination or diffusive separation during the solvent cage life period of the excited species.

Among many other conclusions that can be derived from 'Radical Pair' models one would expect a decrease in photoredox quantum yield in a simple manner with increasing solvent viscosity³. Such decrease in quantum yield has been observed for $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{NO}_2]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Br}]^{2+}$ and many other complexes on 254 nm excitation. But the variations in quantum yield are far too complex to be explained or accounted on the basis of such simple models.

In our case we have, however, found an opposite trend in the photoredox quantum yield in solvents of increasing viscosity on irradiating $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{HC}_2\text{O}_4](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{C}_2\text{O}_4]\text{ClO}_4$ in aquo-glycol media in two different proportions at a fixed pH 3.72 at 35° and at three different wavelengths in both aerobic and anaerobic conditions. The quantum yields, $\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$, ϕ_{NH_3} and ammonia aquated product in anaerobic condition were found to be higher than aerobic conditions as expected (Tables 1 and 2).

Results and Discussion

From Tables 1 and 2 we find that the $\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$ values at pH 3.72 at 35° are higher than those in pure aqueous medium. The yields are higher with increasing organic solvent concentration. At both the concentrations the values of $\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$ are higher in anaerobic condition than the corresponding values in aerobic conditions. The suggested reaction pathways leading to products as shown below, are similar to that by Volger and Adamson⁴.

The same scheme is suggested also for the tetraammine complex.

TABLE 1—QUANTUM YIELDS FOR THE FORMATION OF Co^{2+} , NH_3 AND $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_3\text{C}_2\text{O}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^+$ OF $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{C}_2\text{O}_4]\text{ClO}_4$ USING 366, 313 AND 254 nm RADIATIONS IN AQUEOUS ORGANIC SOLUTION

pH = 3.72, Temp. = 35°

Solvent	Composition % (w/w)	In presence of	$\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$			ϕ_{NH_3}			$\phi_{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_3\text{C}_2\text{O}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^+}$		
			366 nm	313 nm	254 nm	366 nm	313 nm	254 nm	366 nm	313 nm	254 nm
Water	0	Air	0.176	0.278	0.395	1.31	1.25	2.54	0.606	0.138	0.96
		Nitrogen	0.284	0.379	0.602	1.94	1.79	3.02	0.804	0.274	0.61
Ethylene glycol-water	25	Air	0.244	0.301	0.571	1.72	1.57	3.24	0.744	0.366	0.956
		Nitrogen	0.299	0.383	0.624	2.18	1.81	3.76	0.984	0.278	1.26
	50	Air	0.276	0.315	0.592	1.93	1.73	3.66	0.826	0.47	1.29
		Nitrogen	0.332	0.397	0.636	2.31	1.90	4.26	0.982	0.312	1.72

TABLE 2—QUANTUM YIELDS FOR THE FORMATION OF Co^{2+} , NH_3 AND $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{HC}_2\text{O}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{2+}$ OF $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{HC}_2\text{O}_4](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ USING 366, 313 AND 254 nm RADIATIONS IN AQUEOUS GLYCOL SOLUTION

pH = 3.72, Temp. = 35°

Solvent	Composition % (w/w)	In presence of	$\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$			ϕ_{NH_3}			$\phi_{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2\text{HC}_2\text{O}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{2+}}$		
			366 nm	313 nm	254 nm	366 nm	313 nm	254 nm	366 nm	313 nm	254 nm
Water	0	Air	0.262	0.145	0.393	1.73	0.78	3.55	0.42	0.055	1.58
		Nitrogen	0.470	0.199	0.599	3.43	1.08	4.34	1.08	0.07	1.34
Ethylene glycol-water	25	Air	0.361	0.153	0.410	2.11	0.88	4.21	0.31	0.12	2.16
		Nitrogen	0.511	0.201	0.612	3.60	1.10	4.97	1.04	0.10	1.91
	50	Air	0.418	0.161	0.445	2.95	0.93	4.42	0.84	0.13	2.20
		Nitrogen	0.555	0.210	0.637	3.83	1.21	5.53	1.06	0.16	2.33

Aerobic condition :

Anaerobic condition :

The quantum yields of ammonia-aquated product have been evaluated on the basis of material balance,

$$\phi[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^+ \text{ equal to } [\phi_{\text{NH}_3} - 5\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}].$$

The values of $\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$ for the pentaammine complex show complex wavelength dependence, the order being 254 nm > 366 nm > 313 nm in pure aqueous medium and also in the aquo-glycol media at concentrations 25 and 50 wt%. Similar complex wavelength dependence of ϕ_{redox} has been reported⁵ with $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{NCS}]^{2+}$. In case of tetraammine complex the $\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$ however, vary in the manner 254 nm > 313 nm > 366 nm.

In this context it is worth mentioning that both oxalate and thiocyanate ligands have intra-ligand absorption bands (due to transition between molecular orbitals which are localised on the ligand system) in the uv region. These electronic transitions are not charge-transfer transitions but they do frequently occur at energies overlapping appreciably with CTTM and other molecular transitions. In the present work, photolysis of the complexes were carried out at pH 3.72 where the pentaammine oxalato complex may exist in the form of $[(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Co}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)]^+$ and this form has an additional absorption band around 290 nm⁶ compared to the acid form $[(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Co}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4\text{H})]^{2+}$ and this is due to intra-ligand transition. So absorption at 313 nm of the pentaammine complex at pH 3.72 is at least partly due to intra-ligand transition and the lower quantum yield $\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$ at 313 nm is due to the reason that communication between intra-ligand band and the CTTM band is not efficient. The increase in the quantum yield $\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$ compared to that in aqueous medium may be due to various reasons.

From the proposed mechanism we find that in presence of air or oxygen, the $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{\bullet-}$ which is responsible for further reaction with the substrate will be removed resulting in lower $\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$ value. Ethylene glycol which exists in extensive hydrogen-bonded structure, has high viscosity. As a result we may expect the solubility of oxygen in 50

wt% will be low thereby the possibility of the step leading to removal of $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{\bullet-}$ by O_2 will be lowered. As a result the $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{\bullet-}$ may react with the substrate thereby enhancing the quantum yield $\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$. In anaerobic medium as the mechanism suggests there is no question of removal of $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{\bullet-}$ by oxygen and hence the enhanced value of $\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$. This may also be evident from the ratios of $\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$ in aquo-glycol to that in aqueous medium (Table 3). In anaerobic conditions the ratios do not vary much which also gives support to our above mechanism as in presence of oxygen (which will be lower in 50% aquo-glycol than in 25% aquo-glycol) the removal of $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{\bullet-}$ by oxygen will take place in different amounts depending upon different degree of solubilities of oxygen. This suggestion, of course, needs further investigation. The effect of medium on the photoredox yields may also be the result of various other factors : (a) there may be a relatively low energy on set of a CTTM state corresponding to photooxidation of glycol⁵, (b) the effects of medium viscosity and (c) the shape of excited potential energy surface, the binding energies of the CTTM excited state are to a significant extent functions of the solvent environment of complex-ion-substrate.

With mixed solvents (25 and 50 wt% aquo-glycol) there could be preferential solvation of complex ion by water in the aquo-glycol system used. The effect could perhaps make the solvent very inhomogeneous in the immediate neighbourhood of the complex ions with microscopic viscosity values lower than the macroscopic mean one and dependent on the distance from the complex⁷. As a result the radical pair once formed could have diffusive separation rather than cage recombination, thereby increasing the photoredox yield. Since it has been observed that $\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$ for these same complexes decreases with glycerol-water systems with a much lower viscosity than 50 wt% glycol-water and also the values of $\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$ in aquo-glycol are greater than the values in pure aqueous media, it is very difficult to justify the above explanation in terms of microviscosity. Moreover, with pentaammine complex it has been observed that use of ethanol

TABLE 3-RATIOS OF QUANTUM YIELDS OF $\phi_{Co^{2+}}$ IN AQUO-GLYCOL TO THAT IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM AT VARIOUS EXCITING WAVELENGTHS

Complex	% glycol in aqueous media	Condition	Exciting wavelength (nm)		
			366	313	254
[Co(NH ₃) ₅ HC ₂ O ₄] ²⁺	25	Aerobic	1.38	1.05	1.04
		Anaerobic	1.09	1.01	1.02
	50	Aerobic	1.59	1.11	1.13
		Anaerobic	1.18	1.05	1.06
[Co(NH ₃) ₄ C ₂ O ₄] ⁺	25	Aerobic	1.39	1.08	1.45
		Anaerobic	1.06	1.01	1.04
	50	Aerobic	1.57	1.13	1.50
		Anaerobic	1.17	1.05	1.06

in place of glycol does not alter the photo-redox yield compared to that in aqueous media⁸. So it might be prudent to assume that either it is the lesser solubility of oxygen in mixed aquo-glycol system which is responsible for increased $\phi_{Co^{2+}}$ or there may be some sort of specific interaction of the mixed aquo-glycol system with these particular complexes.

Regarding the effect of solvation on the binding energies of the CTTM excited state, it may give rise to activation barrier for radical recombination process, or the thermodynamic enthalpy of forming radical pair may vary with the solvent composition⁵ which could be very specific and this effect should contribute to the binding of the CTTM excited state. Additionally, we can say that the initial excited state following CTTM transitions is left with a solvent environment similar to that of ground state. Since such transitions involve a large change in substrate dipole moment, say from [Co(NH₃)₄C₂O₄]⁺ to [Co(NH₃)₄²⁺.C₂O₄⁻], the thermal equilibration of the CTTM excited state would involve a large adjustment of the solvent environment and must release to solvation appropriate to radical pair species. During the period of adjustment in the solvent environment several photo-physical processes such as electronic relaxation, intersystem crossing etc. affecting the quantum yield can occur within the life-time of the CTTM excited state. Finally, any strong coupling of solvent and substrate (e.g. H-bonding) should affect the rate constant for non-radiative relaxation and therefore the quantum yield for products. These con-

siderations and the above mentioned photochemical observations point to the possibilities that solvent can make substantial contributions to the binding energies of the CTTM excited state and hence can significantly alter the redox yield.

Experimental

The complexes [Co(NH₃)₅HC₂O₄](ClO₄)₂ and [Co(NH₃)₄C₂O₄]ClO₄ were prepared according to the reported methods⁹.

The purity of the complexes were checked by chemical analysis. The uv-visible spectra of the complexes also agreed with spectra reported in the literature. The photolysis of the complexes were carried out at 366, 313 and 254 nm radiation. The 366 and 313 nm were generated from General Electric H₄ lamp and the radiations were isolated from the medium pressure mercury vapour lamp by using a chances O-O filter glass and using a quartz cell containing copper sulphate (2.50 g dm⁻³) for the 366 nm and for 313 nm potassium chromate solution (0.27 g + 1.0 g Na₂CO₃, dm⁻³) along with chances O-O filter. For 254 nm the radiations were generated from low pressure mercury vapour lamp (Thermal Syndicate T/M5/594-110 W).

For photolysis 3.6 ml of the above mentioned complexes in 50 and 25 wt% glycol-water (sodium acetate and acetic acid buffer, pH 3.72) were used. The complex concentration used for 366, 313 and 254 nm were 2.0×10^{-3} , 5×10^{-4} and 1×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ respectively. For deoxygenation, purified nitrogen gas was passed through

a presaturator before bubbling it in the experimental solution. The bubbling of the gas was continued at a very slow rate during photolysis. \

The photoreleased Co^{2+} was estimated using Kitson's method¹⁰ at 625 nm. Ammonia was estimated spectrophotometrically by colorimetric method using Nessler's reagent at 410 nm. The ammonia aquated product was calculated on the basis of material balance. The output of the lamp was measured before and after the experiment by using potassium ferrioxalate actinometry developed by Parker and Hatchard¹¹. The temperature all along was maintained at 35°. The results are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

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